

Pauli Matrices Versus A Vector Dot Product/ Square Root Combination Part II

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In Part I, we argued that the square root of a positive real number bb has a degeneracy, i.e. $-b$ and $+b$ are solutions. Usually one adds \pm by hand, but we argued that there may exist a mathematical formalism which automatically carries this degeneracy. We suggested this formalism involves the three 2×2 Pauli matrices, each of which has eigenvalues -1 and $+1$ associated with this degeneracy for 3-vector components.

Here we suggest that a positive number bb upon which the square root acts, may be thought of as a vector dot product. In other words, b is the vector magnitude, but in a rotated frame one would have (b_x, b_y, b_z) and each of these carry a degeneracy of \pm . A dot product is formally defined as: $\sum_{i,j} b_i b_j \delta_{(i,j)}$, but this equation forces one to add \pm by hand when taking the square root. It simply ensures that there is no mixing of i with j (for i not equal to j).

The relationship for Pauli matrices: $\{s(i), s(j)\} = 2 \delta_{(i,j)} I$ ((A)) (I = identity matrix and $\{$ means anticommutation) may be used to show that the dot product has removed information related to the $+1/-1$ degeneracy. In other words, information inherent to a Pauli matrix, namely its eigenvalues of $+1$ and -1 disappear in ((A)) and so I the 2×2 identity matrix has 2 eigenvectors with the same $+1$ eigenvalue. This is related to the product of two identical Pauli matrices so $+1 * +1 = -1 * -1 = 1$. In other words, $\delta_{(i,j)}$ used in the dot product explicitly loses degeneracy (\pm) information.

Square Roots

The square root of a positive number bb is $-b$ or $+b$. In other words there is a two-fold solution and \pm must be added by hand. One may note that the magnitude of any n -vector, $(b(1), b(2) \dots b(n))$ is: $\sum_{j} b(j)b(j) = \sum_{i,j} b(i)b(j) \delta_{(i,j)}$ where i and j run from 1 to n . In such a case, $b(i)$ and $-b(i)$ yield the same dot product result and it would be good to have this degeneracy appear without having to add it by hand.

There exists a set of three unitary 2×2 matrices, each of which have $+1, -1$ as eigenvalues (1):

$$\begin{matrix} |1 & 0\rangle = s_z & s_x = |0 & 1\rangle & s_y = |0 & -i\rangle \\ |0 & -1\rangle & & |1 & 0\rangle & & |i & 0\rangle \end{matrix} \quad ((1))$$

These matrices carry the $+1, -1$ degeneracy required for a square root, but are only linked with a 3-vector, i.e. (b_x, b_y, b_z) .

They obey the relation: $\{s(i), s(j)\} = 2 \delta_{(i,j)} I$ ((2)) where $\{$ represents anticommutation

and I is the 2×2 identity matrix. We suggest that ((2)) is immediately linked to the vector dot product:

$$B \cdot b = \sum_{i,j} (1 \text{ to } 3) b(i)b(j) \delta_{(i,j)} \quad ((3))$$

In vector analysis a dot product is defined by ((3)). Given a dot product of a vector with itself, however, one must note that there is a degeneracy, namely (+/- bx, +/- by, +/- bz) yields the same dot product result. This degeneracy information is completely lost when using delta(i,j). We further note that:

$I = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$ has two eigenvectors, both with +1 as an eigenvalue

((2)) shows the product of two Pauli matrices and is nonzero only if $i=j$. Each Pauli matrix has +1, -1 eigenvalues, but a product of the same Pauli matrix with itself means that if a Pauli matrix operates on the -1 eigenvector twice, one would obtain +1 as the result. The same result holds for the +1 eigenvector. Thus, information is lost. Two different eigenvalues +1,-1 map into one value +1 when one multiplies two Pauli matrices together which is equivalent to using delta(i,j) which appears in the dot product. The 2x2 identity matrix shows this explicitly as it has two orthonormal eigenvectors with the same eigenvalue, suggesting that something more may be happening.

Thus we argue that the dot product vector formalism loses information (i.e. inherent degeneracy) in a problem involving 3-vector dot products. A physical example of such a 3-vector dot product is $p \cdot p$, where p is the momentum vector. This dot product appears both in the Schrodinger equation and Klein-Gordon equation.

Complete Formalism for a 3-vector Dot Product

We suggest that a complete formalism for a 3-vector dot product should not involve the usual dot product which uses delta(i,j), but rather should depend on Pauli matrices which carry the required degeneracy in the linear form. Thus:

$B \cdot b$ where $b=(b_x,b_y,b_z)$ means the square root is represented by:

$$A = B_x s_x + b_y s_y + b_z s_z \quad ((4))$$

Each $s(i)$ has two eigenvectors with the eigenvalues +1,-1 which accounts for the fact that $b(i)b(i)$ and $-b(i)b(i)$ yield the same result. The $s(i)$ anticommute so

$$A(* \text{ transpose}) A = B \cdot b \quad ((5))$$

$A(* \text{ transpose}) A$ loses the degeneracy information because the +1, -1 eigenvalues map into +1 i.e. B_x and $-B_x$ are two values, but $B_x B_x = -B_x(-B_x)$ which is one value

We note one may interchange $s(i)$ matrices in ((4)). In other words, it seems to be a convention as to which Pauli matrix is called x etc.

We argue that ((2)) shows formally how the vector dot product loses the degeneracy information of +1, -1. Thus when taking a square root, one is forced to add this information by hand.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argued in Part I, that taking the square root of a positive real number bb involves adding \pm by hand to $\pm b$. If b is thought of as the magnitude of a 3-vector, then bb is equivalent to the vector dot product: $b \cdot b = \sum_{i,j} (1 \text{ to } 3) b(i)b(j) \delta(i,j)$. One must add \pm values to $b(i)$ by hand, to show that different vectors yield the same dot product even if $b_x b_x$, $b_y b_y$ and $b_z b_z$ have fixed values.

If one wishes to have the $+1$, -1 solutions appear directly from the mathematics, we suggested in Part I that one use the 2×2 matrix:

$\begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{vmatrix}$ This has two eigenvectors $(1,0)$ and $(0,1)$ with eigenvalues $+1$, -1 .

In (1) we showed that one may find two more 2×2 matrices (unitary) with eigenvalues $+1, -1$ which anticommute.

Here we use the relationship: $\{s(i), s(j)\} = 2 \delta(i,j) I$ ((A)) where $\{ \}$ means anticommutation, to show how the dot product loses the \pm degeneracy information which must then be added by hand when taking a square root. The vector dot product formalism uses $\delta(i,j)$ which is associated with I , the 2×2 identity matrix which has two eigenvalues with the same eigenvalue $+1$. We argue that this already shows that something further is happening.

The relationship ((A)) involves the product of two Pauli matrices and is nonzero only when the two are the same. If the same Pauli matrix acts twice on a particular eigenvector, an eigenvalue of -1 appears twice (multiplied twice) to collapse to $+1$ like the $+1$ eigenvalue and one loses the \pm information when using the vector dot product formalism, applied to two 3-vectors. As a result, for a 3-vector, if one wishes to retain the \pm information, one should express the vector as: $b_x s_x + b_y s_y + b_z s_z$. This retains the orthogonality of the 3-axes as well as the \pm options. The $+1, -1$ options are incorporated in the eigenvalues of each Pauli matrix and only disappear when two identical Pauli matrices are multiplied together, just as $-b$ and b both yield $bb = (-b)(-b)$.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pauli_matrices